

Annex 2: Candidate case studies

These examples are not intended to be replicated exactly. Rather, they illustrate different replication pathways identified through Bio4HUMAN, including institutional, community-based, enterprise, cooperative, and training-centred models. Interested parties should adapt these approaches to local governance, market, environmental, and operational conditions.

Biogas – Kavumu (DRC) VSLA/shared model (SADI/Louvain Cooperation “Mazingira Bora”).

Replication pathway: Service-based and commercially oriented model.

Replicable elements: Biogas framed as a service business, integrated waste collection and treatment approach, potential revenue generation.

Key enabling conditions: Sufficient customer base, business management capacity, regulatory acceptance.

Watch-outs: Affordability for lower-income households, demand aggregation strategies, and regulatory and safety compliance.

Biogas – Kaku Sanitation Services (South Sudan) enterprise model.

Replication pathway: Service-based and commercially oriented enterprise model.

Replicable elements: Biogas framed as a service-based business model with cost recovery and revenue generation, integrated waste collection and treatment approach.

Key enabling conditions: Sufficient demand density, access to start-up capital and business development support, reliable organic waste streams, and basic regulatory clarity for waste handling and energy production.

Watch-outs: Affordability for poorer households, demand aggregation strategies, and regulatory and safety compliance.

Biogas – Yei Hospital (South Sudan) institutional installation.

Replication pathway: Institutional ownership and facility-based service model.

Replicable elements: Clear institutional owner, stable use case for cooking for patients, and potential for scale across facilities.

Key enabling conditions: Dedicated operations and maintenance budget, trained operations staff and access to technical support, strong facility management ownership, and reliable and sufficient feedstock.

Watch-outs: Long-term maintenance and replacement planning.

BSF – INERA reference hub + AALI support (DRC).

Replication pathway: Training, technical support and demonstration hub.

Replicable elements: Reference strain maintenance, free training and technical support, and expansion through partnerships.

Key enabling conditions: Continued institutional capacity to maintain the reference hub, access to appropriate equipment, reliable partnerships, and secure operating conditions.

Watch-outs: Insecurity disrupting operations, need for periodic strain refresh, and equipment gaps including collection, shredding, and drying.

BSF – COPANYA women’s cooperative (DRC).

Replication pathway: Cooperative livelihood and local circular enterprise model.

Replicable elements: Cooperative model, dual outputs from larvae feed and fertilizer, and livelihood benefits.

Key enabling conditions: Reliable supply of segregated organic waste, cooperative governance capacity, market access for outputs, and basic technical and business support.

Watch-outs: Market competition with imported feed, pricing pressures from subsidised chemical fertilizers, and the need for reliable segregated organic waste supply.

BSF – MORJITA (South Sudan) ToT model with UNHCR support.

Replication pathway: Training-of-trainers and cooperative formalisation model.

Replicable elements: Training-of-trainers approach, cooperative formalisation, and reported revenue generation.

Key enabling conditions: Access to water, ongoing mentoring, cooperative governance, and market access for outputs.

Watch-outs: Dry-season water constraints can halt production, and business and financial management skills are required alongside technical training.